

FORUM Report: Connections in Computational Proteomics

V3.0

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1. Forum background and event summary

The Australian BioCommons facilitated this forum to unite proteomics experts with Australian researchers, bioinformaticians and service providers at 'Connections in Computational Proteomics' on the 30th and 31st of January 2024.¹

The forum was open to all and took place in Melbourne during the lead up to the Lorne Proteomics 2024 conference. The event was designed to allow the computational proteomics community to discuss challenges and potential solutions to these challenges, explore interactive analysis tools and preview the Galaxy Australia Proteomics Lab.²

The aims of the forum were to provide a space where participants could:

- **Network** with other proteomics researchers and computational proteomics specialists
- **Hear the perspectives** of leaders in proteomics
- **Contribute** to strategic discussions
- **Help inform** an ongoing national response to resolve challenges in computational proteomics
- **Get hands on** with Galaxy Australia and Proteomics Lab
- **Discuss** best practice interactive tools for proteomics
- **Learn more** about the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Bioinformatics Community
- **Have the opportunity to get involved** in future work

A full program is available in **Appendix 1**. The slides for the forum are available in the Zenodo entry.

¹ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/proteomics-connections>

² Proteomics Lab on Galaxy Australia <https://proteomics.usegalaxy.org.au/>

2. Introductions and updates on in-flight activities

Attendees were introduced to the Australian BioCommons project³ and the engagement process with the Australian Proteomics Bioinformatics community. **Figure 1** highlights the structure of this process, including steps taken to identify and research the community, communicate and consult with community members, distil community requirements from these consultations into a Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia,⁴ and begin the deployment of solutions or activities that address the challenges described in the roadmap (see also **Table 1**).

Figure 1. The Australian BioCommons community engagement process,⁵ which includes **1)** the identification of a community, **2)** researching a community, **3)** communicating with members of the community, **4)** distilling the results of communication and consultation into a roadmap document, and **5)** deploying potential solutions (see also **Table 1**).⁶

³ Australian BioCommons <https://www.biocommons.org.au/>

⁴ Gustafsson, O. J. R., & Christiansen, J. (2022). Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia (4.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7460249>

⁵ Tiffanie Nelson, Andrew Lonie, *et al.* (2021, March 1). The Australian BioCommons Community Engagement Strategy: Understanding community-scale challenges to inform solution delivery. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4569256>

⁶ <https://proteomics.usegalaxy.org.au/>

Table 1. Solutions or current activities addressing the Australian proteomics bioinformatics infrastructure roadmap.

Solution / Activity	Related roadmap deliverable	How to get involved
Proteomics Lab on Galaxy Australia ⁷	D1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses D2. Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration	Join the Proteomics Lab working group ⁸
Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLES) ⁹ eg. Scaling DIA-NN to HPC ¹⁰ on the Gadi system ¹¹ at the NCI ¹²	D1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses	Get involved with ABLeS ¹³
Training specific to computational proteomics eg. Getting started with proteomics webinar ¹⁴	D4. A proteomics-specific training program	Join the quarterly community meeting ¹⁵

3. Invited speaker presentations

Three invited expert speakers presented their perspectives on challenges in computational proteomics at the forum:

- **Prof Dr Mathias Wilhelm:** Computational Mass Spectrometry, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9224-3258>
- **Paula Burton:** CEO and Co-Founder of Mass Dynamics <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5783-6528>
- **Prof Dr Stefan Tenzer:** Immunoproteomics, University Medical Center of the Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3034-0017>

⁷ Proteomics Lab on Galaxy Australia <https://proteomics.usegalaxy.org.au/>

⁸ Visit this page for more information: <https://www.biocommons.org.au/proteomics-community>

⁹ Gustafsson, O. J. R. et al. (2023). Enabling national step changes in bioinformatics through ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139651>

¹⁰ High performance computing (HPC)

¹¹ Scalable DIA-NN <https://github.com/Sydney-Informatics-Hub/Scalable-DIA-NN>

¹² National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) <https://nci.org.au/>

¹³ Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLES) <https://www.biocommons.org.au/ables>

¹⁴ Padula, M. et al. (2023). WEBINAR: Getting started with proteomics. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019318>

¹⁵ Proteomics Community Meeting <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1eaiAvRTGndpHhg9mFFexugd2Z39QEARnOGusAghYEc/>

4. Interactive sessions

Multiple interactive sessions were held at the forum, consisting of mini presentations and breakout group discussions. Session results and summaries of the breakout group discussions are provided below.

4.1 Strategic discussion - challenges in computational proteomics

Participants identified and discussed challenges that are facing computational proteomics in Australia, in the context of the previous sessions, and based on the following guiding topics:

- **Proteomics users**
 - Bioinformaticians
 - Those who need bioinformatics, but are not bioinformaticians
 - Researchers who understand proteomics, but don't code
 - Other groups that don't understand proteomics, and may not code
- **Intricate / complex proteomics**
 - Analysing and making sense of the data
 - Being clear about complexity in experimental design vs. the bioinformatics required
 - Understanding limitations of datasets
- **Understanding global best practices**
 - Curated set of trustworthy packages / tools (endorsed)
- **Where is data kept?**
 - Cross-institutional challenges to data access
 - Sharing data at the end of a project
 - Meeting journal requirements
- **Any other ideas and observations**

Five major challenge areas were prominent when the comments from the breakout group discussions were distilled. These are also illustrated in **Figure 2**.

1. **Speaking the same language:** Multiple comments indicated that there is a language barrier between bioinformaticians, biologists, information technology (IT), and business. On the user side, this manifests as high expectations that need to be managed, a need for information and training that is tailored to beginners (eg. curated collections), and well described outputs (eg. what is a protein group?) that adhere to the open data expectations in biology. The comment that researchers are “drowning in PDFs” resonates here and, together with the language barrier described, suggests that the community aspiration to enable and accelerate knowledge sharing is critical.
2. **Designing a meaningful experiment:** Best practice experimental design was mentioned as a challenge, as was the current inability to combine different sample cohorts and different methods. This is particularly problematic given the range of experiment types that are possible in proteomics, including but not limited to instrumentation, software versioning and even computational hardware variations.

3. Reproducible analyses:

- a. **Software and workflows:** The use of multiple packages and knowing which package is best were highlighted as challenges. This is further complicated by a broad range of user skill sets (eg. DIA-NN¹⁶ outputs can be difficult to further analyse), and the number of possible data outputs / interpretations that can be produced by software (ie. as inputs and / or versions change). The re-analysis challenge was also discussed: the need to repeat experiments, analyses, or both as new mass spectrometers or associated technology are deployed. Related to this point was a requirement for reproducibility, including standardised workflows that can reproduce analyses, and the availability of test data sets with well-known “ground-truth” results (eg. label free quantitation [LFQ] bench experimental datasets and the Australasian Core Facilities initiative).
 - b. **Compute:** Discussions also focused on the challenge of managing compute infrastructure and in particular the scaling of compute. Cost of cloud solutions (including downloads/uploads/storage) was raised as well, although the current usage footprint of proteomics on other systems, including high performance computing (HPC),¹⁷ is unknown. The cost of compute as measured across the lifespan of specific mass spectrometry instruments and the security of data were also discussed.
4. **Clarifying the meaning of output data:** The ability to make proteomics output data relatable to life scientists was discussed, including making it clear “what is really increasing”, linking results to concrete concepts such as copies per cell, data set normalisation and pathway analysis.
 5. **Organising and sharing data outputs and their context:** Multiple challenges were discussed relating to data sharing, and included difficulty in sourcing adequate metadata to understand the context for proteomics repository data, and an explosion of file formats. Problematic network speeds are adding to this challenge, particularly for the download of large files (> 100 GB) from repositories such as PRIDE.¹⁸ The absence of Cloudstor¹⁹ is having an impact here, and there was interest in replacement solutions like Globus.²⁰ Proteomics data files are growing in size, with new instruments like the Astral²¹ (i.e. up to 30 GB of data per hour) and TimsTOF²² able to produce 10s of GB per hour, presenting long term data transfer and storage challenges. Potential solutions were highlighted, including mass spectrometer level pre-processing to dump noise (already integrated on the Astral), and pre-filtering raw data using machine learning approaches. Training and infrastructure to support data management (ie. organisation, and also topography²³) were also raised, in particular how this management can connect / translate to better devops, sci-ops (concept introduced during forum), increased speed, and knowledge retention through consistent staff support and retention.

¹⁶ Demichev, V., Messner, C.B., *et al.* DIA-NN: neural networks and interference correction enable deep proteome coverage in high throughput. *Nat Methods* 17, 41–44 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0638-x> & <https://bio.tools/DIA-NN>

¹⁷ E.g. Setonix HPC at Pawsey Supercomputing Centre <https://pawsey.org.au/systems/setonix/>

¹⁸ Proteomics Identification Database (PRIDE) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>

¹⁹ <https://support.aarnet.edu.au/hc/en-us/sections/6547442372367-CloudStor-Decommission> - note that AARNet has launched FileSender as a standalone service: <https://www.aarnet.edu.au/filesender>

²⁰ Globus <https://www.globus.org/>

²¹ Orbitrap Astral Mass Spectrometer

<https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-syst-ems/orbitrap-lc-ms/orbitrap-astral-mass-spectrometer.html>

²² timsTOF <https://www.bruker.com/en/products-and-solutions/mass-spectrometry/timstof.html>

²³ Topography - data, workflows, IT, outputs

Figure 2. Five major challenge areas noted during the breakout group session for the strategic discussion of challenges in computational proteomics. These were “speaking the same language”, “designing a meaningful experiment”, “reproducible analyses”, “clarifying the meaning of output data”, and “organising and sharing data outputs and their context”. Each challenge area has example notes added that reflect the individual comments made during the session.

4.2 Preview of a shared platform for computational proteomics (Galaxy Australia and Proteomics Lab)

The Proteomics Lab session included an introduction to Galaxy Australia,²⁴ presented by Dr. Anna Syme, followed by dedicated time for onboarding and exploration for both Galaxy Australia and Proteomics Lab, as well as breakout group discussion and feedback. The session was supported by a pre-prepared Galaxy history²⁵ featuring a quantitative proteomics tutorial²⁶ from the Galaxy Training Network (GTN)²⁷ and a dedicated computational allocation that made use of Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS).²⁸ The distilled feedback to questions asked during the breakout group discussion is included here.

- **Is Proteomics Lab a good idea?** Yes! However, it needs more work to streamline.
- **What does Proteomics Lab enable?** The service enables a simpler entry point to Galaxy Australia, and mostly benefits new users of the service.
- **What can be improved?** The group recommended moving the three tiles (i.e. Alphafold 2.0²⁹ application, tool and data request, and additional storage) lower on the main service page, in order to prioritise the tools available.
- **What is missing?** The participants requested that the tools list on the left side should be more organised and tailored to proteomics. Tools for re-scoring and deep learning re-analysis were noted as missing from Galaxy (“a whole field of tools is missing”). Similarly, the participants wanted to be able to view spectra using Galaxy, and “drill down” from protein and peptide identities to spectra and fragments. It was noted that there is a “fine line of functionality” and, if they were made available, standardised clean workflows could alleviate the challenge of access to a large set of tools.

New tool sections were also suggested by one group as part of an improved layout for the Proteomics Lab page (see **Figure 3**). The new sections would be:

- **Data dependent acquisition (DDA) standardised tools:** MaxQuant,³⁰ MSstats³¹, LFQ-Analyst³²
- **Data independent acquisition (DIA) standardised tools:** DIA-NN, MSstats, DIA-Analyst³³

²⁴ Galaxy Australia <https://usegalaxy.org.au/>

²⁵ <https://usegalaxy.org.au/u/johan/h/maxquant-and-msstats-for-the-analysis-of-label-free-data>

²⁶ Melanie Föll, Matthias Fahrner, MaxQuant and MSstats for the analysis of label-free data (Galaxy Training Materials). <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/proteomics/tutorials/maxquant-msstats-dda-lfq/tutorial.html> Online; accessed Tue Feb 27 2024

²⁷ Hiltmann, S., Rasche, H. et al. Galaxy Training: A Powerful Framework for Teaching! PLOS Computational Biology (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010752>

²⁸ Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS) <https://www.biocommons.org.au/training-infrastructure>

²⁹ https://bio.tools/alphafold_2 & Jumper, J., Evans, R., Pritzel, A. et al. Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. Nature 596, 583–589 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2>

³⁰ MaxQuant <https://www.maxquant.org/> / <https://bio.tools/maxquant> & Cox, J., Mann, M. MaxQuant enables high peptide identification rates, individualized p.p.b.-range mass accuracies and proteome-wide protein quantification. Nat Biotechnol 26, 1367–1372 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.1511>

³¹ Choi M, Chang CY, et al. MSstats: an R package for statistical analysis of quantitative mass spectrometry-based proteomic experiments. Bioinformatics. 2014 Sep 1;30(17):2524-6. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu305>

³² Shah, A.D., Goode, R.J.A., et al. LFQ-Analyst: An Easy-To-Use Interactive Web Platform To Analyze and Visualize Label-Free Proteomics Data Preprocessed with MaxQuant. Journal of Proteome Research 19 (1), 204-211 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.9b00496>

³³ DIA-Analyst <https://analyst-suites.org/apps/dia-analyst/>

- **DDA tandem mass tags (TMT):**³⁴ MaxQuant, MSFragger,³⁵ TMT-Analyst³⁶
- **Other:** eg. Metaproteomics (e.g. I-Metalab³⁷) DDA LFQ and stable isotope labelling by amino acids in cell culture (SILAC)³⁸ tools. Utilise Maxquant for DDA and DIA-NN for DIA.

The group also recommended adding the citation instructions for all tools included in Proteomics Lab.

Welcome to the Galaxy Australia Proteomics Lab. Get quick access to the tools, workflows and tutorials you need to get started with proteomics on Galaxy.
[What is this page?](#)

This page is currently under development in consultation with the Australian Proteomics Bioinformatics community.

Proteomics tutorials for Galaxy | MS data file format converters | MS reference data on Galaxy

AlphaFold 2.0 on Galaxy Australia
Apply now

9000+ Tools & Datasets Ready to install
Request now

Additional storage Available on request
Request now

Quantitative proteomics

Tools Help

Some example tools are listed here: you can also search for more in the full tool panel to the left.

MaxQuant

FlashLFQ

Post processing and visualisation

Tools Help

Some example tools are listed here: you can also search for more in the full tool panel to the left.

LFQ Analyst

MSstats

Figure 3. Proteomics Lab on Galaxy Australia.

³⁴ Thompson, A., Schäfer, *et al.* Tandem mass tags: a novel quantification strategy for comparative analysis of complex protein mixtures by MS/MS. *Analytical chemistry*, 75(8), 1895-1904 (2003) <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac0262560>

³⁵ <https://bio.tools/msfragger> & Kong, A., Leprevost, F., *et al.* MSFragger: ultrafast and comprehensive peptide identification in mass spectrometry-based proteomics. *Nat Methods* 14, 513–520 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.4256>

³⁶ TMT-Analyst <https://analyst-suites.org/apps/tmt-analyst/>

³⁷ Li, Leyuan, Zhibin Ning, *et al.* iMetaLab Suite: A one-stop toolset for metaproteomics. *iMeta* 1, e25 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/imt2.25>

³⁸ Ong, S. E., Blagoev, B., *et al.* Stable isotope labeling by amino acids in cell culture, SILAC, as a simple and accurate approach to expression proteomics. *Molecular & cellular proteomics*, 1(5), 376-386 (2002) <https://doi.org/10.1074/mcp.M200025-MCP200>

4.3 Addressing challenges researchers face when visualising and interpreting proteomics data

For the purposes of the discussion at the forum, interactive tools for proteomics were defined as tools that allow a researcher to draw meaning from their proteomics data, either by post-processing the data (ie. tabular quantitative information), or allow visualisation / exploration of the data. To set the scene for this session, Dr. Pouya Faridi and Dr. Ralf Schittenhelm from Monash University presented an overview of how interactive tools are defined, and their typical features as tools change from open format (ie. highly flexible sandbox tools with many options) to linear (ie. pipelined tools suited to a specific task).

The brief introduction was followed by a mini poll for the participants, which was aimed at gaining a landscape view of interactive tool usage by the group. The poll results are described in [Table 2](#).

Table 2. Results of the mini poll focused on interactive tools for proteomics.
There were a total of 12 participants in the poll.

Question	Result
<p>What area of proteomics or metabolomics research are you involved in?</p> <p>12 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proteomics: n = 12 (43%) ● Peptidomics: n = 5 (18%) ● Phosphoproteomics: n = 5 (18%) ● Metabolomics: n = 4 (14%) ● Glycoproteomics: n = 2 (7%) ● Other: n = 0
<p>Did you know what interactive tools were before this meeting?</p> <p>12 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes: n = 11 (92%) ● No: n = 1 (8%)
<p>Do you use interactive tools for proteomics?</p> <p>12 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes: n = 12 (100%) ● No: n = 0
<p>If you answered NO, why don't you use interactive tools?</p> <p>1 response</p>	<p>I don't know how to use interactive tools effectively</p> <p>Other possible responses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I don't need to use interactive tools for my analyses ● I can't access the interactive tools I need for my analyses ● The available tools are not fit-for-purpose (eg. they are tailored to model organisms)

<p>If you answered YES, what interactive tools do you currently use?</p> <p>9 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Spectronaut:³⁹ n = 4 ● Perseus:⁴⁰ n = 3 ● Proteome Discoverer:⁴¹ n = 3 ● Analyst Suites:⁴² n = 2 ● Peaks:⁴³ n = 2 ● R:⁴⁴ n = 2 ● N = 1 response each: Cytoscape,⁴⁵ DIA-NN, gProfileR,⁴⁶ FragPipe,⁴⁷ in house shiny app, Mass Dynamics,⁴⁸ MaxQuant, most pathway databases, MSFragger, Oktoberfest,⁴⁹ Python,⁵⁰ and Unipept⁵¹
<p>What do current interactive tools do well?</p> <p>8 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Intuitive user interface (UI) ● Filtering ● Quick and easy ● Pathway analysis ● Quantification ● Visualisations ● Really depends on the tool ● Showing basic info about data ● Making Volcano plots quickly ● Interactive data exploration - i.e. select a data point in a Volcano plot and interrogate further
<p>What do current interactive tools NOT do well?</p> <p>8 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● They are not transparent with respect to their assumptions. It can be hard to understand when to apply, and when not to ● Black boxes ● Combining different types of proteomics data, such as whole proteome and phosphoproteomics analysis ● Some are proprietary ● Some are too complex ● Often no data integration

³⁹ BIOGNOSYS Spectronaut <https://biognosys.com/software/spectronaut/>

⁴⁰ Perseus <https://www.maxquant.org/perseus/> / <https://bio.tools/perseus> & Cox J., Mann M. 1D and 2D annotation enrichment: a statistical method integrating quantitative proteomics with complementary high-throughput data. BMC Bioinformatics. 2012;13 Suppl 16(Suppl 16):S12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-13-S16-S12>

⁴¹ ThermoFisher Scientific Proteome Discoverer

<https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/multi-omics-data-analysis/proteome-discoverer-software.html>

⁴² Analyst Suites <https://analyst-suite.monash-proteomics.cloud.edu.au/>

⁴³ Bioinformatics Solutions Peaks Studio <https://www.bioinfor.com/peaks-studio/>

⁴⁴ The R Project for Statistical Computing (2024). <https://www.r-project.org/> & R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing (2024). <https://www.R-project.org>

⁴⁵ <https://bio.tools/cytoscape> & Shannon, P., Markiel, A., *et al.* Cytoscape: a software environment for integrated models of biomolecular interaction networks. Genome research, 13(11), 2498-2504 (2003). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1101/gr.1239303>

⁴⁶ https://bio.tools/gprofile_r & Reimand, J., Arak, T., *et al.* g:Profiler—a web server for functional interpretation of gene lists (2016 update), Nucleic Acids Research, Volume 44, Issue W1, 8 July 2016, Pages W83–W89, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw199>

⁴⁷ <https://fraggpipe.nesvilab.org/> & Yu, F., Teo, G.C., *et al.* Analysis of DIA proteomics data using MSFragger-DIA and FragPipe computational platform. Nat Commun 14, 4154 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39869-5>

⁴⁸ Mass Dynamics <https://www.massdynamics.com/>

⁴⁹ Picciani, M., Gabriel, W., Giurcoiu, V. G., Shouman, O., Hamood, F., Lautenbacher, L., Jensen, C. B., Müller, J., Kalhor, M., Soleymaniyi, A., Kuster, B., The, M., & Wilhelm, M. Oktoberfest: Open-source spectral library generation and rescoring pipeline based on ProSit. Proteomics, 00, e2300112 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/pmhc.202300112>

⁵⁰ Python <https://www.python.org/>

⁵¹ <https://bio.tools/unipept> & Mesuere, B., Willems, T., *et al.* Unipept web services for metaproteomics analysis, Bioinformatics, Volume 32, Issue 11, June 2016, Pages 1746–1748, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btw039>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Really depends on the tool, choosing tool based on what I want to achieve ● Deal with more complicated comparisons, better graphics which are more customisable, not crash, version integration ● Enrichment visualisations
<p>Is there anything else missing in this space?</p> <p>6 responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Galaxy needs interactive exploration of data ● Quality control (QC) ● Packages for further pathway analysis of post-translational modifications (PTMs) other than phosphoproteomics and further analysis of peptidomics data ● Better description of tools required to use them, bioinformatics workflows need to be better described in publications ● Nicer graphics, different types of graphs, better UI ● Multi omic tool

The comments from the breakout groups reflected the results of the mini poll and the strategic discussion session. The challenges raised in the context of interactive tools included:

- **The measurement technology** itself (ie. mass spectrometry).
- **Accessing the contextual metadata** required. One participant commented that “to interpret data well you must know about 50 metadata descriptors”.
- **Communicating the uncertainty** of proteomics: this seems to be tied to a disconnect between protein and peptide level analyses, and the observation that top peptides are not enough. There is a loss of information.
- **A lack of guidance** on how to apply bioinformatics to proteomics: researchers need to understand how to pick the right tool, get this tool running on the right hardware specification, and know how to make use of tools that are frankly too complex (ie. too many input options, and manuals / documentation are often missing).
- **Standardised data formats** are not being used.
- **Uploads to repositories** are too time consuming and need to be streamlined.

When asked if a researcher needs to be able to program to work in proteomics, it was noted by participants that bioinformatics knowledge is more important than programming, and even though dedicated bioinformatics courses are missing, teaching should include bioinformatics for proteomics. In addition, close collaboration is required to create final products (eg. programming help to modify tools) and this often takes a team (ie. researchers, software engineers, and statisticians). This also means that appreciation and credit for coders and their expertise is needed, and in this context the group were asked to consider if they are research software engineers (RSEs).⁵²

Finally, the following elements were considered to be missing in the interactive tools space:

- **Interactive multiomics** (including integration).
- **Gene ontology**: usually need to switch programs to access this capability.

⁵² Research Software Engineers (RSE) <https://researchsoftware.org/>

- **End-to-end analysis options:** although end-to-end solutions were discussed and some analytical processes are considered to belong together (eg. search and quantitation), it was noted that software for primary analysis can be complex. It may therefore be better to keep some tools separate and modular, such that each tool is well suited to one part of an analysis.
- The ability to **help end users such as clinicians** (ie. through detection of proteins in specific samples).
- A **free tool for peptide coverage graphs:** transcriptomics might have a read pile up tool that performs the same function and which can be repurposed.

Multiple ideas and challenges that reflected earlier conversations were also raised. These included incorporating user ideas and perspectives (ie. using packages as a user), creating standardised pipelines / workflows, quality control for tabular data outputs, combining different output types, that the “Australian Galaxy initiative is great!”, that documentation is often missing for tools, and finally that approaches other than false discovery rate (FDR) should be considered (eg. QC based on precision value quantification).

5. Next steps for the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Bioinformatics Community: 2024 and beyond

The BioCommons helps to coordinate a community for computational proteomics and bioinformatics,⁵³ which aims to:

- **Engage** with Australian proteomics researchers, bioinformaticians and their collaborators
- **Provide a forum** for the community to share knowledge, connect and collaborate
- **Work with the community** to understand the bioinformatics challenges specific to computational proteomics
- **Identify gaps** in the community scale digital infrastructure available for proteomics
- **Co-create, align to, or adapt** best practice solutions that address these challenges and that can be maintained in collaboration with local and international infrastructures.

BioCommons engages with this group to collaboratively address community-identified challenges, including resolving gaps in the digital infrastructure available for proteomics research.

Based on the outcomes of the forum, distilled in this report, the following activities are proposed for 2024:

1. Continue the quarterly meeting series.
2. Launch version 1 of Proteomics Lab, based on feedback collected during the forum.
3. Set up themes for quarterly meetings, based on the categories highlighted in the strategic discussion: **1)** speaking the same language, **2)** designing a meaningful experiment, **3)** reproducible analyses, **4)** clarifying the meaning of output data, and **5)** organising and sharing data outputs and their context.
4. Use these themes to focus the activities that aim to resolve challenges for computational proteomics.

⁵³ Australian BioCommons Proteomics Bioinformatics Community <https://www.biocommons.org.au/proteomics-community>

6. Acknowledgements

The organisers would like to acknowledge the following groups for making the forum a success:

- The computational proteomics community in Australia!
- Australasian Core Facilities (ACF) group
- University of Melbourne⁵⁴
- Lorne Proteomics 2024 organising committee⁵⁵
- Australasian Proteomics Society (APS)⁵⁶
- Sydney Informatics Hub⁵⁷
- National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)
- Galaxy Australia

Appendix 1 - Forum program

Day 1: Tue 30 Jan 2024	
Time	Activity
12:00	Lunch provided
13:00	Welcome and introductions
13:20	Invited speaker presentations & ask me anything Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Prof Dr Mathias Wilhelm, Computational Mass Spectrometry, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany• Paula Burton, CEO and Co-Founder of Mass Dynamics• Prof Dr Stefan Tenzer, Immunoproteomics, University Medical Center of the Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Germany
14:35	Afternoon tea and networking
15:00	Strategic discussion: Addressing the key challenges in computational proteomics
16:00	Interactive session: Preview of a shared platform for computational proteomics (Galaxy Australia and Proteomics Lab)
17:00	Wrap up of day 1
17:10	End of day 1

⁵⁴ University of Melbourne <https://www.unimelb.edu.au/>

⁵⁵ Lorne Proteomics 2024 <https://www.lorneproteomics.org/>

⁵⁶ Australasian Proteomics Society (APS) <https://www.australasianproteomics.org/>

⁵⁷ Sydney Informatics Hub <https://www.sydney.edu.au/research/facilities/sydney-informatics-hub.html>

18:00	Group dinner (at your own expense)
Day 2: Wed 31 Jan 2024	
Time	Activity
8:30	Morning coffee
9:00	Interactive session: Addressing challenges researchers face when visualising and interpreting proteomics data
10:00	Morning tea and networking
10:30	Next steps for the Australian BioCommons Proteomics Bioinformatics Community ⁵⁸ : 2024 and beyond
11:00	Meeting close & walk to bus stop for trip to Lorne Proteomics

Document Control

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	DESCRIPTION
1.0	19-03-2024	Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson	Initial version
2.0	27-03-2024	Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson	Incorporated forum participant feedback
3.0	05-04-2024	Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson	Add contributors

⁵⁸ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/proteomics-community>